

Study and modeling of soil erosion processes under artificial rainfall conditions

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Soil erosion on agricultural lands leads to reduced productivity and intensification of degradation processes. Therefore, modeling soil washing and identifying its main factors are of significant scientific and practical importance. In this study, a special laboratory device was developed to investigate erosion processes under artificial rainfall conditions in different soil types, and an authorship certificate was obtained. Methodologically, the device allows for water supply from a 200-liter reservoir to rainfall sprayers, artificial setting of slope angles (5°, 10°, 15°, 20°), and measurement of the washed soil mass using an electronic balance and filter paper.

The experiments used 48 soil monoliths (dark gray, mountain brown carbonate, typical, and leached soils). Rainfall parameters were set at intensities of 2–4 mm/min with a duration of 20 minutes.

The results showed that slope angle and rainfall intensity are the main determinants of soil washing. For example, in dark gray soils at an intensity of 2 mm/min and a 5° slope, soil washing amounted to 0.3982 t/ha, whereas at a 20° slope this increased to 1.4089 t/ha. When rainfall intensity was 4 mm/min at a 20° slope, washing reached 1.7705 t/ha. Accordingly, soil erosion processes were found to intensify proportionally with increasing slope. Across different soil types, erosion levels varied significantly: mountain brown carbonate soils showed higher washing, while leached soils exhibited relatively lower rates.

Raindrop diameter (0.2–4.5 mm) also had varying effects on erosion processes: drops in the 1.5–3.0 mm range caused soil aggregate breakdown, decreased permeability, and formation of compacted crusts. As a result, soil water infiltration decreased and the mass of the washed layer increased sharply.

In conclusion, the artificial rainfall method is an effective model for studying soil erosion processes under laboratory conditions, and the obtained data serve as a basis for developing scientifically grounded recommendations on soil protection. Such studies are of great importance for sustainable use of water resources and maintaining the productivity of agricultural lands.

References

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